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Compatibilities of University Entrepreneurship Program and Students' Entrepreneurial Characteristics in Indonesia

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Abstract

University entrepreneurship programs in Indonesia have been rapidly developed under the policy Merdeka Belajar Kampus Merdeka. This article analyzes the compatibility of university entrepreneurship programs and students' entrepreneurial characteristics. A mixed method based on sequential approach was used as research methodology. The data were collected through Focus Group Discussion and interview with stake holder, practitioner, and academicians. The finding of research shows that the dimension of the compatibility of entrepreneurship program to millennial generation should pay attention to adaptive entrepreneurship education material, instructor's experience, teaching method, the compatibility of science background, socialization of program, creating a business ecosystem, ease and flexible of budget management, legal assistance, business orientation, discretion in solving the problem, entrepreneurial mindset, business research, and facilitation. The recommendation given is that to improve the entrepreneurship program, a dynamic entrepreneurship program is required in all Universities in Indonesia corresponding to the millennial generation's needs in post-industrial society.

Keywords: Higher Education, Entrepreneurship Programs, Entrepreneurial Characteristics

1. Introduction

Covid-19 pandemic situation beginning to occur in early 2020 in Indonesia generates a variety of economic problem. One of which is the potential estimated increase in unemployment rate from 2.91 million to 5.23 million in 2020 in Indonesia, according to data of National Economic Recovery Program (Indonesian: Program Pemulihan Nasional or PEN) (Pemulihan Ekonomi Nasional, 2020). Therefore, a sustainable economic recovery attempt taken by government is to reduce national unemployment rate through adapting the education orientation to the reality in work and industrial realms. State universities are expected to produce graduates ready for working

independently and according to the demand of work realm today. The attempt is in line with Ministry of Education and Culture arranging a Freedom-to-Learn – Independent Campus program aiming to encourage the development of each education unit, the adjustment of learning process condition in academic, cultural, local wisdom, social-economic, and infrastructural system aspects.

In this case, government takes an attempt of implementing the education-oriented economic improvement by encouraging the students, as the agent of change, to adapt to work realm in order to improve the human resource competency. It is intended to prepare demographic bonus that will expectedly occur in 2020-2035 (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2013). The data collected shows that there is still an increase in open unemployment rate among the graduates of universities by 1.27% in February 2020 - February 2021. Particularly in February 2021, the total unemployment rate of university graduates is 6.97% (Hermawan, 2016). The fact is a problem arising related to the course of entrepreneurship education and program in universities that has not achieved the outcome as expected in relation to the educated unemployment rate.

Entrepreneurship program has been prepared for being a part of other governmental programs held by Education, Research and Technology Ministry such as internship activity, independent study, student exchange, Student Study Service for building village, assistance, and humanity project through Freedom-to-Learn – Independent Campus (Indonesian: Merdeka Belajar Kampus Belajar or MBKM) (Jenderal et al., 2020). Particularly, the learning process and various entrepreneurship education developments at universities can direct entrepreneurship attitude to the more positive one and to affect significant the students' entrepreneurship behavior (Rudi Irwansyah & Lulup Endah Tripalupi, n.d.). The government does so as an attempt of encouraging the students to have academic knowledge and complex practical experience in entrepreneurship when they study in the university.

The government's attempt of preparing qualified human resource based on Government Regulation Number 17 of 2010 about Education Management and Organization stating that high education aims, among others, to create faithful and pious, knowledgeable, competent, skillful, critical, creative, innovative, health, independent, self-confidence, tolerant, socially sensitive, and responsible humans. In its implementation, a further review should be conducted on the sustainability of entrepreneurship program to millennial student as the basic target of the improvement of competency in entrepreneur development practice in order to be appropriate-target corresponding to the millennial students' entrepreneurial preference. Regarding this, the concept of entrepreneurship for students should be adjusted with technology change and various social issues occurring recently.

2. Method

The author selects millennial-generation students to be the subject of primary data in this research, the students born in 1992 – 2012. The combination between millennial and zillennials generations shows similar characteristics that can distinguish them from the previous generation. Adolescents born in that year become the early Indonesian generation of adolescent adaptation equally feeling various big transitions in learning cyberspace, social media, digital world, and technology. Thus, specifically, the students admitted to the universities in 2017-2021 who have passed through the adaptation process and any challenges of business development in the digital era and various social issues within it.

The characteristics of social entrepreneurs coming from the millennial generation can be seen from the research (Zhang et al., 2021). Identifying millennial generation through perseverance, proactive personality, concern for social problem, internal life satisfaction standard as self-motivation, and self-efficacy. The literature review delivered (Kusumawardhani, n.d.) found that there is a positive constructive effect on the creation of entrepreneurial intention through personal attitude, education support, and social media use. Previous research conducted (Rodriguez et al., 2019) found that courage and hard work shown by millennials can strengthen entrepreneurial attitude and loyalty. The identification process is continued to find the dimension of the compatibility of entrepreneurship programs to the millennial generation in Indonesia. It becomes the state of the art of this research if the compatibility is explored to entrepreneurship programs needed by millennial students in Indonesia.

This research aims to analyze the suitability of entrepreneurship programs in State Universities by seeing millennials, academicians, practitioners, and many parties including stakeholders related to entrepreneurship development for the millennial generation. Theoretically, the approach used is post-industrial society seeing modern society development building more on training and education provisions based on personal service and skill (Daniel Bell, 2020). Conceptually, the bottom-up design approach is used to put the millennial-generation students to be the main subject of research entitled to participate in the development of Indonesian education policy and programs.

2.1. Research Design

This research employed mixed methods; the research design chosen was the explanatory sequential design. The process of collecting data was conducted through hybrid (online and offline) Focus Group Discussion, in-depth interviews, and online questionnaire distribution. The research design chosen was the explanatory sequential design. This pattern is called a two-phase design (Creswell, 2002).

2.2. Sample

The result of observation on the student's perception was conducted in June 2021 by distributing an online questionnaire to the students in 75 state universities in Indonesia, with a total of 3920 respondents was used for the process of analyzing quantitative data to obtain the data of the millennial generation's entrepreneurial preference. A qualitative approach is conducted through hybrid (online and offline) FGD and in-depth interviews with the students selected using the purposive sampling technique, consisting of 114 students coming from 10 (ten) State Universities in and out of Java Island. The analysis process can be continuous until the data are considered as having been qualified to be categorized systematically.

3. Results and Discussions

The result of the online questionnaire was obtained from 3920 respondent students in State Universities. The millennial entrepreneurial characteristics can be seen from the perception of students as the actor participating in entrepreneurship program activities at State University.

3.1. Characteristics of Respondents

The template is designed so that author affiliations are not repeated each time for multiple authors of the same affiliation. Please keep your affiliations as succinct as possible (for example, do not differentiate among departments of the same organization). This template was designed for two affiliations. The majority of respondents are millennial students born in 1999-2003. In this research, the ratio of students enrolled in State Universities in Java Island to those out of Java Island completing the online questionnaire concerning millennial entrepreneurial characteristics is fairly equal (58%:42%). This composition of respondents is expected to represent the actual condition in the field. By major group, majority respondents (66%) are students coming from the social and humanities group, while the rest of (34%) are those coming from the Science and Technology group.

3.2. Respondents' Perception

In this study, individual respondents should answer 5 (five) question items. The items of question were scored using the Likert scale (1-5). From the result of quantitative data, the respondents' response to the questions posed by the author is presented in the table 1 below.

Table 1: Statistic Data Result of Online Questionnaire Question Items

Millennial Entrepreneur Indicators	Entrepreneurial Tendency Score Based on the Year of Birth of the Millennial Generation in Indonesia					Mean	Interpretation
	1999 n=33	2000 n=71	2001 n=12	2002 n=11	2003 n=41		
	7	7	87	61	8		
Perseverance							
I determine the target of the task regularly	4,02	4,04	4,09	4,11	4,09	4,07	High
Business routines are essential in entrepreneurship	4,16	4,16	4,13	4,17	4,07	4,13	High
Proactive Personality							
I am interested in the entrepreneurship course	3,83	3,78	3,75	3,63	3,51	3,70	High
I am waiting for orders from the lecturer while studying independently	3,21	3,16	3,12	3,15	3,15	3,15	Moderate
Concern for social problem							
Environmental issues are considered in the business plan	4,15	4,15	4,12	4,13	4,00	4,11	High
I follow national developments regularly	3,63	3,62	3,60	3,60	3,54	3,59	High
Life Satisfaction							
I procrastinate doing heavy tasks	3,27	3,21	3,26	3,35	3,38	3,29	Moderate
Self Efficacy							
I feel talented to be an entrepreneur	3,47	3,47	3,34	3,36	3,32	3,39	High
Entrepreneurs can bring social change for the better	4,33	4,31	4,31	4,30	4,32	4,31	Very High
Digital Literacy							
I feel proud of my social media accounts	3,47	3,38	3,36	3,44	3,31	3,39	High
Business Motivation							
Entrepreneurs can develop their capacity	4,34	4,31	4,32	4,33	4,32	4,32	Very High
Professional work has low time flexibility	4,33	2,84	2,87	2,84	2,97	3,17	High
I will set up a business that matches my hobby	4,20	4,11	4,12	4,13	4,11	4,13	Moderate High
Critical Attitude							
Successful entrepreneurs tend to be apathetic	3,50	3,61	3,56	3,44	3,48	3,51	High
I prefer to follow other people's directions	3,10	3,14	3,12	3,14	3,45	3,19	Moderate

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

In Quantitative data, millennials tend to have high persistence maximum value scale of 5. The data shows that the millennial education process tends to be neutral to wait for orders from lecturers (3.15). In achieving life satisfaction, millennials are at a moderate trend (3.29). Millennials are also in a neutral position to receive directions from others (3.19). Millennial motivation is still in a neutral position to be able to work professionally (3.17). The various neutral tendencies of the millennial generation obtained from quantitative data became the basis for conducting FGD activities and in-depth interviews to find programs needed by the millennial generation to give them confidence in their future orientation. Dimensional findings were obtained after getting perspectives from millennials regarding entrepreneurship learning, involvement in entrepreneurship programs, academic and practitioner perspectives, and seeing the role models of entrepreneurship programs that have been carried out.

3.3. Students' View on Entrepreneurship Learning Process

Qualitative data collected from millennials shows that the students who are attending education in State University perceived that the entrepreneurship education process through entrepreneurship course remains to be desirable. It is an important factor in growing the interest in being entrepreneurship among the millennials through the academic process.

Therefore, in its sustainability, University should stimulate a systematic entrepreneurship education. Millennial students give some inputs concerning the entrepreneurship learning they have obtained from attending the entrepreneurship education in the campus. The participation of facilitator with complex competency including

cognitive competency and practitioners strongly experienced with entrepreneurship learning process becomes important to millennial students. The main objective of job opportunity creation delivered by the millennial students in developing entrepreneurial skill can be considered as the millennial generation's high motivation to develop their entrepreneurial spirit.

Millennials really expect the participation of practitioners and the reinforcement of experiential practice in entrepreneurship learning. In other condition, the millennials' comments imply the mentoring process sustainability during the entrepreneurship learning. Therefore, an advanced entrepreneurship learning design is required to be the early formulation of policy in term of the development of the students' entrepreneurial interest and talent. Furthermore, some students state that the participation of mentor mastering entrepreneurship field either academically or practically is desirable to support the students' freedom of thinking in deciding various entrepreneurial ideas. In State Universities, despite different characteristics of study programs, such disciplines as social humanities and science and technology remain to be important to obtain the foundation of entrepreneurship learning. Also, the millennials' input seems to be related to the process of integrating entrepreneurship material into the learning in campus. The integration process can be done by leading the knowledge on entrepreneurship to the positive social effect like digital-preneur and knowledge on market development can be described at table 2 below.

Table 2: Analysis of the students' view on entrepreneurship learning on the campus

Dimension	Analysis of the Millennial students' View
Adaptive entrepreneurship education material	Entrepreneurship learning is still considered important, but the material should be adapted to business development today to know the market well
Instructor's experience	Entrepreneur Academician & practitioner professional in entrepreneurship
Teaching Method	Being interested more in the practical approach to entrepreneurship
The compatibility of science background	Millennial students with social humanities and science and technology disciplines still need entrepreneurship according to their focus

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

3.4. Students' Experience and Expectation for Attending Entrepreneurship Program in Campus

In universities, students have various opportunities of participating in entrepreneurial program activities. The following result presents a perspective based on the experience and participation of students in the entrepreneurship program on the campus. It shows that millennial students tend to have perseverance. It implies that millennial students are very adaptive to the quality of entrepreneurship programs delivered to them. The entrepreneurship program provided should be able to accommodate all the needs of businesses operated by millennials, due to varying target markets.

Socialization process should run well and acceptable from upstream to downstream or study program to enable the students to give their best potency to apply for fund to various schemes of entrepreneurship programs existing. Basically, millennial pay much attention to the information accepted concerning the offering of entrepreneurship program. The early spirit of millennials should be followed up immediately before they think of business planning too far, because they can be overthinking when they think of the business plan themselves. Millennials with high motivation should be supported with structured facilitation. Adequate time for the millennials to prepare themselves will result in good business planning, for example through the business proposal joining the competition. Another constraint encountered by millennial in the planning process when attending the competition of entrepreneurship program, the millennial students need supporting facilitation in designing and allocating budget during attending the entrepreneurship program.

Although millennials have many business ideas, without structured facilitation to see the constraints encountered, they will implement them less maximally. The optimization of entrepreneurship program develops more maximally in state universities if it is supported with facilitation involving training, mentoring and facilitator to fulfill the need of students attending this program. The facilitation is also conducted by academician and practitioners experienced in entrepreneurship field to direct the students later according to systematical stage. Entrepreneurship program in State Universities should pay attention to external cooperation based on community including alumni business community or the community established independently by students, cooperation with community and industry beyond the campus.

Table 3: Analysis of the experience and expectations of students who attend the entrepreneurship program on campus

Dimension	Socialization of Program	Creating Business ecosystem	Ease and Flexible of Budget Management	Legal Assistance	Business Orientation	Discretion in Solving Problem
Analysis	Distribution of Information should be done routinely to all students. Millennials still have creative ideas that haven't materialized yet.	Collaboration should be made among the parties or internal and external stakeholders to support the establishment of a business community organization with a broad network	A flexible approach must be given so that millennial students do not experience difficulties in terms of budget management, cash flow organization, and financial report writing	Millennial students want the campus to help legalize the product, obtain intellectual property right to the product, and register the business permission	There should be a change of mindset in entrepreneurship programs for millennial students, from the money-oriented to the socially-oriented one.	Try to give students many opportunities for facilitation and business collaboration to increase their experience with solving various social problems using an independent campus approach

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

3.5. Practitioner's and Academicians' Perspective View

An entrepreneurial process is a very long one, in which millennials do not develop in the condition of strong field experience. In this case, the University should be able to identify the students' potency in such a way that has entrepreneurial passion and spirit as it is not easy. The university should, among others, be able to encourage the students to have negotiating ability in terms of product development. It can strengthen the personality of a millennial entrepreneur to be a multidisciplinary entrepreneur.

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An attempt taken by the government, through the Ministry of Education and Culture, is to launch the Freedom-to-Learn – Independent Campus programs, one of which is the entrepreneurship program. The practitioners see this as an opportunity. Entrepreneurship program implemented in State University can be developed in the Freedom-to-Learn – Independent Campus curriculum to facilitate the program giving the millennial students an opportunity of developing their creativity according to time challenges today.

Academicians play important role in strengthening the basis of entrepreneurship knowledge through theoretical explanation and the direction of entrepreneurship concept insight. In early conditions, millennials have not been aware of the potency they have, but their development process academicians motivate those who have interest and talent in entrepreneurship to learn more deeply the good business knowledge base. The big potency the millennials have can facilitate the actors of education, in this campus and academicians, in the term of preparing the appropriate program. Millennials' high motivation should be welcomed by a good entrepreneurial education ecosystem.

Table 4: Analysis of Stakeholder's view on Entrepreneurship Program for the millennial generation.

Dimension	Practitioner	Academician
Entrepreneurial Mindset	It is important to prepare mentality of entrepreneurial spirit in a broad sense	The delivery of appropriate teaching methods affects positively the millennials' interest
Business Research	Business innovation should be based on market research	Evaluative research should be conducted to strengthen entrepreneurship education and practice.
Facilitation	Business incubator programs should be consistent with time development, by using technological skills the millennials have.	Monitoring should be conducted sustainably to see the business development process implemented by millennials.

Source: Processed Primary Data (2021)

3.6. Role Modeling of Entrepreneurship Program in State University

Support is given to entrepreneurship programs in Indonesia as an attempt of developing an entrepreneurial spirit that has been implemented by universities since a long time ago. Many strategies and models are applied expected to make the students interested in learning and participating in a variety of entrepreneurship programs. Recently, the role modeling of entrepreneurship programs through reinforcing the entrepreneurship learning process and incubation approach has been implemented well in various universities. For example, the attempt has been taken by Universitas Sebelas Maret, through the Directorate of Innovation and downstream, to establish UNS innovation Hub constituting an institution to commercialize the result of the invention, research, and innovation. UNS Innovation Hub also gives millennial students an opportunity of developing a new idea, channel various creativities, and help the acceleration of business ecosystem and startup incubation development. In its process, UNS Innovation Hub has a program structure operating in 3 channels: (1) Pre-incubation conducted to screen the potential tenants, (2) incubation conducted to develop individual and tenant's talent, and (3) post-incubation expected to accelerate the development of startup and to be given an opportunity of getting advanced fund along with Business Management Agency (BPU).

In terms of product legalization produced by millennial students, UNS Innovation Hub facilitates the millennial students to have intellectual property (HKI, KI, PT, etc) through the business tenant. It is very helpful to the millennial students in the aspect of acceptance and recognition of product quality in the public. The students attending the incubation program held by UNS Innovation Hub answer the needs for millennials in developing their potency through systematic mentoring and monitoring processes. Universities should adjust the business ecosystem with the millennials' needs; the self-confidence the millennials have should be maximized through concrete entrepreneurship facilitation and giving many benefits. Supporting education implemented in the university environment as the entrepreneurship education institution contributes positively to the development of entrepreneurship broadly (Fayolle et al., 2014). The structured ecosystem of the university has highly affected the entrepreneurship intention (Moraes et al., 2018). In this case, the campus should always make adequate adaptations to accommodate the millennial students' needs, and the campus also can facilitate it through the program in line with the interest and talent of students with diverse backgrounds.

The millennial students have high perseverance, as indicated with so many programs initiated by students to make a change into the better one today. Perseverance and spirit are desirable as they believe in an individual's capability to achieve the long-term objective (Duckworth et al., 2007). A proactive personality gives an individual to be responsible for identifying business opportunities by understanding the procedure to embark on business (Neneh, 2019). A proactive individual is a figure always developing culture intensely in finding opportunity (Chipeta et al., n.d.). The support of education is related directly to entrepreneurship intention (Turker & Selcuk, 2009). Developed and developing societies should know social entrepreneurship as a global phenomenon and should identify further the similarity and the difference between different contexts within it (Zhang et al., 2021). Intellectual capital is an important factor in increasing personal knowledge and working more efficiently and productively (Alshebami & Seraj, 2021). University is the highest educational institution that can create millennial students mastering academic fields and having complex skills concerning social entrepreneurship. Such a condition is very desirable to face a demographic bonus in the next few years.

Some factors like knowledge, experience, bond, attitude, social norm, perceived behavioral control, and personalities affect positively the entrepreneurial intention in the millennial generation (Koe et al., 2012). Millennials prefer being guided by a mentor to get some inputs (Berkup, 2014). The entrepreneurial intention will get stronger if the attitude an individual has is supported with stronger education (Kusumawardhany, n.d.). Millennials want a comprehensive facilitation process from mentoring to monitoring processes when they hold entrepreneurship learning. Life satisfaction can be managed by millennials having encountered many constraints. Millennials' dissatisfaction with their career or experience can motivate them to develop themselves in entrepreneurship activity (Shaw & Carter, 2007). The entrepreneurship approach should shift from traditional practice to a holistic teaching process; the main key is the development of behavior through an entrepreneurial mindset (Daniel, 2016). The mobility process affects positively innovation and entrepreneurial orientation in a university (Civera et al., 2020). Through the freedom-to-learn-independent campus system, the university can provide freedom opportunities through providing space for creative ideas, volition, thinking, and soul, and giving the millennial generation to develop according to their potency and ability.

The entrepreneurial mental ability can be created when universities can adjust the need with the characteristics of the millennial generation. It can be synchronized with the post-industrialist society dimension theory approach suggested by Daniel Bell (Daniel Bell, 2020). The preference found in entrepreneurial youngsters in the service sector is compatible with the post-industrialist economic structure (Martynova et al., 2017). Post-industrialist society to date concentrates more on the reinforcement of education or knowledge to generate new and bright ideas or innovation. Entrepreneurship growth is very important to the post-industrial environment because of the absence of entrepreneurial culture constructed in an ecosystem, various difficulties will be faced in the adaptation process (Gherhes et al., 2018). The entrepreneurship education process can encourage the improvement of an individual's entrepreneurial competency (Koe, 2016). The ecosystem constructed through a business incubator is perceived to bear future-oriented millennial generations as an attempt of solving the problems arising in the future challenge.

From the results of the entrepreneurship role model program analysis above, the entrepreneurship program launched by the State University can be said to be an appropriate program for the millennial generation who have a high tendency of Millennial Social Entrepreneurial characteristics. It takes several dimensional approaches derived from the needs of millennial entrepreneurs to provide opportunities for millennial students who need to strengthen their self-confidence to become entrepreneurs. In developing the Freedom-to-Learn – Independent Campus program, through the entrepreneurial program approach implemented by each university, it must adjust the needs and characteristics expected by the millennial generations.

Figure 1: The model of the suitability of the entrepreneurship program with the millennial generation in Indonesia.

The dimensions of the compatibility of entrepreneurship program to the millennial generation that should be taken into account by the entrepreneurship program in implementing its activities are adaptive entrepreneurship education material, instructor's experience, teaching method, the compatibility of science background, socialization of program, creating a business ecosystem, ease and flexible of budget management, legal assistance, business orientation, discretion in solving the problem, entrepreneurial mindset, business research, and facilitation.

Considering the result of research and discussion, the entrepreneurship program delivered by the State Universities is compatible with the entrepreneurial preference of the millennial generation and desirable to post-industrial society era. It can be seen from the role model of entrepreneurship programs implemented in universities. Its development is expected to strengthen the entrepreneurial potency the millennials have in academic facilitation and practice, particularly through a strong business ecosystem such as creating various business incubators corresponding to the millennials' needs.

Thus, an analysis of the suitability of various entrepreneurship programs in universities is suitable for millennials who have a high tendency, but universities must provide a different approach for other millennial characters to have the confidence to be involved in various entrepreneurship programs. The entrepreneurship program is expected to collaborate with the Freedom-to-Learn – Independent Campus curriculum and to be the bridge between universities to give the millennial students an opportunity of choosing the entrepreneurship program needed according to each interest.

The results of this study can be used as an alternative for universities to adjust entrepreneurship programs according to the dimensions of the needs of the millennial generation. Recommendations for further research are to focus on identifying entrepreneurship programs that follow the changing millennial characteristics of each university by approaching the social, economic, and cultural conditions of the local area.

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